

An Innovation Searching for Analyzing the Israel & Top Chinese Cities GDP Status & the Global Universities in 2020~2025 by Sustainability

Run Xu^{1*}, Zhenguo Li²

^{1*}Gyeongsang National University, School of Nano New Materials Engineering, Jinju-Si 52828, Gyeongsangnam-Do, South Korea.

²Yanshan University, School of Electrical Engineering, Qinhuangdao 066000, Hebei Province, China.

*** Correspondence:** Run Xu

Received: 05-March-2026

Accepted: 15-March-2026

Published: 17-March-2026

Copyright © 2026, Authors retain copyright. Licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/> (CC BY 4.0 deed)

This article is published in the **MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management (MSIJEBM)**

ISSN 3049-141X (Online).

The journal is managed and published by MSI Publishers.

Volume: 3, Issue: 3 (March-2026)

ABSTRACT: The high-tech product is able to increase the GDP ratio gradually according to developing situation presently. It is to believe that the ratio will raise a certain one in near future because it has high-knowledge & high-science factors within knowing it to producing it from the transfer of laboratory to factory. So that the new product enables us to exhibit in its market after it was made in a factory continuously through using our scientist and engineers' behaviour positively. We must encourage the high-tech proceeding engineers etc. who will transform the idea stimulus into the searching behaviour in lab with other researchers through acquiring a certain project from the funding so as to erect the experience and knowledge after several years that makes the sample into product entering current market to complete the receiving the order and transiting the cuisine to customers. That will be said that automatic changing to artificial intelligence one in order to promote the time and efficiency at all through the huge change said, "let it do" changed to "it can do". we should continuously enhance its function and upgrade it & make its stability, that means it can undergo a long time to serve as a humanoid

robot that may sometimes be exhibited in our canteen as an automatic and artificial intelligence one to save some money while promoting its quality and efficiency concept. Thereby, the GDP increasement will coordinate the infrastructure and industrial innovation, and the latter will include high-technique product making ones. We may continually improve our capacity to make a new high-level product for the sake of promoting our industrial development with a certain value each year. The other one will be foreign trade exportation that may help us earn the foreign money to use in later urgent time. So, the industry, learning, research & usefulness etc. will be boosting that combines into university, institution, factory& office four aspects cooperative spirits and culture for the sake of building a good future.

Keywords: *innovation; the Israel & Top Chinese Cities GDP Status; the Global Universities in 2020~20253; analyzing; searching.*

1. Introduction

The nations & regions GDP will represent their comprehensive strength in views of economy level and quality, so searching it may have an important effectiveness for us to process statistic with the national producing amount every month, season and year. In the meantime, the value with y-y has also a significant meaning that reflects the economic growth step because we should clarify the increasing change so as to evaluate the increasement and decline value preciously. The positive y-y value may mean the good and rapidly developing status whilst the minus one may state the bad and slow economy step. So, we judge the economy developing enhancement and decreasement through that y-y value for a certain period. Thereby, the detail discussion will include in the following aspects. The GDP which indicates national economic status has provided an important role in every aspect in the world. So that the population increasing rate would be maintained for the sake of raising high-technique product with the entire industrial chain constantly which might enhance our new-quality-productivity. Hence we should consider the effective factors for example the population quantity, new quality productivity with high-technique etc. like big plane electric vehicle battery AI robot quantum computer medicine making disease diagnosis AI (artificial intelligence), ocean source space exploration nuclear generator etc. other ones. Low population is enable to offer high life & quality with

improving GDP per capita value. Meanwhile, it can enhance the national whole GDP value and help us to boost the economic recovery and many things to do. So the certain population is about to improve our national confidence some degree and make us to become priority one as early as possible even the super-country to lead the world to leadership right.

In contrast, the GDP increasing rate may play a significant role with regulating population increasing rate mutually and cooperatively. Hence the two aspects may be emphasized and paid attention to in thriving the whole national economic developed degree through enough wielding our generations positively and efficiently by our government institution endeavor and evaluation. For the sake of making relevant policies and allocating capital into the necessary industries the corresponding strategic plan needs to be made under various background and entities. Then the according monitor and estimation will be followed and estimated periodically and frequently by the observer in government's institution. At last, as to the developed speed in one nation the corresponding population increasing quantity and high-technique product producing will be discussed and considered more preciously and correctly according to the near past years experience and variation. [1~16]

2. Discussions

In this paper the detail GDP value is going to be discussed as above parts through comparing the various regions for the sake of enhancing corresponding tactic in next year and futural several years. Eventually the regional GDP will be compared with their variation and then confidently make a strategic plan for concluding the past years and erecting new target that we pay much attention to raise our predicting value all the time. It is clarified that with regulating our aim the good achievement will be finishing in future that makes us to be more confident year by year for the sake of realizing the plan at present and in certain future. On the other side, we should learn and develop relevant project and subject to reveal the core one after their phenomena. Then we master that technique to apply to that kind of substance making ability through the engineers and scientists transformed to the R & D (research & development) department in makers. Therein, a sample will change into launch product by us to search for which may bring out new functional precise and quick

responding to our request up to now. We should continue developing our similar functional equipment continually.

2.1 The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison

The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison might show 80~119 billion yuan by Hangzhou~Chongqing cities respectively to record their forwards steps in 1995 in light of Figure 1. In contrast, the Tianjin, Suzhou & Shenzhen cities followed the Chongqing occupied the second~forth position.

Figure 1. The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison. [1]

2.2 The petroleum reserving part nations' analysis

The petroleum reserved part nations' analysis might show 440~50 billion barrels and 440~50 billion dollars by Vietnam~Turkey in 2026 in light of Figure 2 to exhibit the Vietnam, Egypt etc. the enough petroleum reservation. On the contrary, the Italy remained 58 billion barrels to record the lower ones following Turkey.

Figure 2. The petroleum reserved part nations' comparison. [2]

2.3 The global universities analysis in 2020~2025

The QS global universities analysis in 2020~2025 might show 23~20 by Peking University and 15~20 by Tsinghua University respectively to show the Tsinghua University a little higher reputation than Peking University.

Figure 3. The global universities analysis in 2020~2025. [3]

On the other hand, the Times higher educational global universities analysis in 2020~2025 might show 23~13 by Peking University and 20~12 by Tsinghua University respectively to show the Tsinghua University a little higher reputation than Peking University.

Figure 4. The Times higher educational global universities analysis in 2020~2025. [3]

On the other hand, the US global universities analysis in 2020~2025 might show 51~31 by Peking University and 28~16 by Tsinghua University respectively to show the Tsinghua University somewhat higher reputation than Peking University.

Figure 5. The US News global universities analysis in 2020~2025. [3]

At last, the SS global universities analysis in 2020~2025 might show 45~24 by Peking University and 28~22 by Tsinghua University respectively to show the Tsinghua University somewhat higher reputation than Peking University.

Figure 6. The Soft Science global universities analysis in 2020~2024. [3]

Overview, we need to continue to search those cutting-edge-fields through our experts and scientists because those aspects may be sustained specially in low-contamination non fossil fuel like wind energy photovoltaic energy hydraulic one nuclear reacting-pile one. So we need a lot of engineers & scholars etc. participating cooperatively and satisfy the producing learning searching & usefulness series of industrial procedures to invest and push into market meeting consumers demands. There will be still big resilient space to wield our imagination and research capacity to publish the relevant achievement in famous journals so as to arouse the basis & application aspects research together for alleviating the cause matters. We should continue to search and develop the low-carbon energy base status and application to futural huge requirement electricity for example the chargeable battery technique etc. reserved energy stations which increases from several years gradually meeting the electrical vehicle hybrid vehicle even small motorcycles.

3. Conclusions

The high-tech product is able to increase the GDP ratio gradually according to developing situation presently. It is to believe that the ratio will raise a certain one in near future because it has high-knowledge & high-science factor within knowing it to producing it from the transfer of laboratory to factory. So that the new product enables to exhibit in its market after it was made in a factory continuously through using our scientist and engineers behaviour positively. We must encourage the high-tech proceeding engineers etc. who will transform the idea stimulus into the searching behaviour in lab with other researchers through acquiring a certain project from the funding so as to erect the experience and knowledge after several years that makes the sample into product entering current market to complete the receiving the order and transiting the cuisine to customers. That will be said that automatic changing to artificial intelligence one in order to promote the time and efficiency at all through the huge change said “let it do” changed to “it can do”. we should continuously enhance its function and upgrade it & make its stability that means it can undergo a long time to serve as a like humanoid robot that may sometimes exhibit in our canteen as an automatic and artificial intelligence one to save some money while promoting its quality and efficiency concept. Thereby, the GDP increasement will coordinate the infrastructure and industrial innovation, and the latter includes high-technique product making ones. We may continually improve our capacity to make a new high-level product for the sake of promoting our industrial development with a certain value each year. The other one will be foreign trade exportation that may help us earn the foreign money to use in later urgent time. So the industry, learning, research & usefulness etc. procedures will be boosting that combines into university, institution, factory & office four aspects cooperative spirits and culture for the sake of building a good future.

Funding

This work was supported by the Korean Science & Engineering Fund (KSEF) at the granted No. 96-0300-11-01-03 under the Specified Basis Research program.

Ethic Declarations

The authors declared that there were not conflicts of interest.

References

1. The Israel & top Chinese cities GDP comparison, Mar 13, 2026
2. The petroleum reserving nations analysis, Mar 13, 2026
3. The global universities analysis, Mar 13, 2026
4. Run Xu1*, Zhenguo Li, An Innovation Searching for Enhancing the China Foreign Trade Trillion Yuan provinces Value & Chinese Master Graduated Application Number on Scientists Sustainably I,MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research,Volume-3, Issue-3 (March-2026), 1~12, <https://zenodo.org/records/18921905>
5. Run Xu1*, Zhenguo Li,An Innovation Searching for Increasing the Chinese Cities' GDP & per capita Value on Scientists Sustainably,MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management, Volume-3, Issue-3 (March -2026), 1~12, <https://zenodo.org/records/18921450>
6. Run Xu1*, Zhenguo Li,An Innovation Searching for Enhancing the China Foreign Trade Trillion Yuan provinces Value & Chinese Master Graduated Application Number on Scientists Sustainably,MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research,Volume-3, Issue-3 (March-2026), 1~11, <https://zenodo.org/records/18922272> Impact Factor: 4.0
7. Run Xu1*, Zhenguo Li,An Innovation Searching for Analyzing & Enhancing the Chinese Provinces GDP & Five Metropolitan Cities GDP Value, MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management, Volume-3, Issue-3 (March -2026), 1~12, <https://zenodo.org/records/18944812>
8. Run Xu1*, Zhenguo Li,An Innovation Searching for Analyzing & Enhancing the Chinese Top Provinces' GDP & Subject for the Archives of Engineering and

- Technology,MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management, Volume-3, Issue-3 (March -2026), 1~12, [https://zenodo.org/ records/ 18944889](https://zenodo.org/records/18944889)
9. Run Xu, Jing Yu, Guanghui Yu, Jianguang Liu, Xianglan Piao, Changfu Jin, Zheman Lian, Dezhu Li,An Innovation Searching for Chinese provinces GDP Value analysis,MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research,Volume-3, Issue-3 (March-2026), 1~11, <https://zenodo.org/records/18944950> Impact Factor: 4.0
 10. Run Xu, Jing Yu, Guanghui Yu, Jianguang Liu, Xianglan Piao, Changfu Jin, Zheman Lian, Dezhu Li,An Innovation Searching for Analyzing Five Metropolitan Cities GDP Value, MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research,Volume-3, Issue-3 (March-2026), 1~11, [https://zenodo.org /records/18945054](https://zenodo.org/records/18945054) Impact Factor: 4.0
 11. Run Xu, The Searching for Analyzing the Nation's Economy Strength GDP and The Top Nations' Industrial Production Comparison Sustainably through Observing Historical Statistic Value, MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research,Volume-3, Issue-3 (March-2026), 1~11, [https://zenodo.org/ records/ 18853698](https://zenodo.org/records/18853698) Impact Factor: 4.0
 12. Run Xu, The Searching for Analyzing the Nation's Economy Strength GDP & Top Nations' Industrial Production Comparison & China cities index of development etc. Sustainably through Observing Historical Statistic Value, MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research,Volume-3, Issue-3 (March-2026), 1~11, <https://zenodo.org/records/18853807>
 13. Run Xu^{1*}, Zhenguo Li,An Innovation Searching for Analyzing & Enhancing the Chinese Provinces GDP & Five Metropolitan Cities GDP Value, MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management, Volume-3, Issue-3 (March -2026), 1~12, [https://zenodo.org/ records/ 18944812](https://zenodo.org/records/18944812)
 14. Run Xu^{1*}, Zhenguo Li,An Innovation Searching for Analyzing & Enhancing the Chinese Top Provinces' GDP & Subject for the Archives of Engineering and Technology,MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management, Volume-3, Issue-3 (March -2026), 1~12, [https://zenodo.org/ records/ 18944889](https://zenodo.org/records/18944889)

15. Run Xu, Jing Yu, Guanghui Yu, Jianguang Liu, Xianglan Piao, Changfu Jin, Zheman Lian, Dezhu Li, An Innovation Searching for Chinese provinces GDP Value analysis, MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, Volume-3, Issue-3 (March-2026), 1~11, <https://zenodo.org/records/18944950>
16. Run Xu, Jing Yu, Guanghui Yu, Jianguang Liu, Xianglan Piao, Changfu Jin, Zheman Lian, Dezhu Li, An Innovation Searching for Analyzing Five Metropolitan Cities GDP Value, MSI Journal of Multidisciplinary Research, Volume-3, Issue-3 (March-2026), 1~11, <https://zenodo.org/records/18945054> Impact Factor: 4.0